

Tilts in Energy and Trade Patterns in the Wake of Pandemic and Urbanization in Case of the United Kingdom

Ramsha Anwer

Ph.D. Scholar, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

Tayyaba Naveed

Ph.D. Scholar, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

Muhammad Zahir Faridi (Corresponding Author)

Professor, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

Atiq Ur Rehman

Ph.D. Scholar, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

Rubab Anwar

M.Phil. Scholar, Scholar, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

Khawaja Asif Mehmood

Assistant Professor, School of Economics, Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan 60800, Pakistan

ABSTRACT: Environmental deterioration is considered as a burgeoning issue that humanity must tackle. In fact, it is recognized as one of the emerging issues of the 21st century globally. This investigation of the escalating issue which offers unique insights into the situation in the United Kingdom. In a time, series spanning the years 2001–2021, Carbon-dioxide (CO₂) is the dependent variable, while urbanization, trade openness and renewable energy are the independent variables. The results of the NARDL model indicate both symmetrical as well as asymmetrical perspectives. There persists significant but negative association among urbanization and CO₂ emissions because at reaching certain point more urbanization leads to a lesser affected levels created by CO₂ emissions, and individuals thus turn to renewable energy to reduce their environmental impact. Moreover, a non-linear result has been discovered between urbanization and CO₂ emissions. Additionally, there exists a significant symmetric as well as asymmetric association between CO₂ and renewable energy consumption in long-run. As far as trade openness is concerned, the dependent variable shows a positive and insignificant association with it. The energy consumption numbers throughout the time period also indicate a shift away from non-renewable fuels and toward renewable energy sources. Last but not least, the paper suggests to utilizing renewable energy and transitioning to efficient technologies as the means of addressing the destruction.

Keywords: Environment, Carbon-dioxide, Urbanization, Trade Openness, Renewable Energy, Energy Consumption.

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1. Introduction

Energy shortages and environmental deterioration are at the top of the list of humanity's numerous concerns to be resolved. It is largely recognized as the worldwide issue of this century (Gokmenoglu et al., 2021). The acceleration of climate change, ecological disruption, and developmental asymmetry, all of which contribute to the destruction of the ecosystem, are attributable to humans. A key indicator of environmental degradation'- carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions (Alola et al., 2019), have increased by 45 percent over the past 13 decades (Bekun et al., 2019). Due to the enforced global lockdowns during the recent pandemic outbreak in the first quarter of 2020, CO₂ emissions have globally decreased by 6.4 percent to a total of 2.3 billion tons (Tollefson, 2021). Countries have worldwide reduced their emissions by an average of 17 percent compared to the previous year (Le Quere et al., 2020). Ironically, the fall in emissions is both less and shorter-lived than what experts had projected. As soon as the virus was contained, economic activity resumed rapidly, resulting in a resumption of the previous increasing trend in CO₂ emissions. However, research suggests that human activities have not yet returned to their pre-COVID-19 levels (Faridi et al., 2022), which offers a bigger environmental risk because emissions are increasing faster than human activities (Foster, 2021).

The United Kingdom was one country that was heavily afflicted by the pandemic. On an average of 10 days, the number of confirmed cases of COVID-19 increased from two in January to about 10,000 on March 25, 2020, and then to 50,000 on April 25 and 100,000 on April 16 (Shresta & Lohani, 2020). Widespread criticism has been placed on the British government's delay in enacting a thorough lockdown as a prompt response to the outbreak. Inadequate testing and a lack of appropriate equipment for personal care are also factors. By July 2021, around 5.6 million cases of COVID-19 were documented in the United Kingdom, with almost 130,000 deaths.

However, excess mortality provided a more comprehensive view of the pandemic's effects than a simple tally of cases and deaths. The high incidence of COVID-19 resulted in positive environmental results, such as reduced CO₂ emissions. Recent declines in CO₂ emissions are most likely attributable to improvements in energy efficiency and an increase in the use of renewable energy sources. Despite significant progress, the per capita emissions in 2019 were 5.3 tons, higher than the global average but lower than the EU's (Evans, 2020). The United Kingdom is now the fourth-largest emitter of CO₂ worldwide. By 2020, renewable energy will account for 42 percent of the United Kingdom's electrical supply, compared to 41 percent for fossil fuels (Ambrose, 2021). Multiple initiatives, including the Renewable Obligation and the Feed-in Tariff, is introduced for promoting the usage of energy in the form of electricity (Energy, 2019). In 2020, energy from renewable sources will overtake energy from fossil fuels for the first time in the United Kingdom, illustrating the exceptional returns on investment in this area.

The United Kingdom adopted the most ambitious targets for lowering CO₂ emissions in April 2021 and by 2035, they intend to reduce emissions by a whopping 78 percent. In addition, as part of a 2019 amendment to the Climate Change Act, the United Kingdom set a goal of zero emissions by the year 2050. Alternatively, this is the same as aiming for a

100 percent reduction in emissions. According to a report by the Energy and Climate Intelligence Unit, the UK government established a number of policies in order to reach this objective. It has a record of consistently prioritizing these objectives of security, affordability, and de-carbonization in its energy policy. By 2030, the proportion of electricity generated from renewable sources is expected to surpass 50 percent (IEA, 2019). According to the Energy and Economic Growth (EEG) Report (2020), the generation capacity is predicted to decline by 13 percent in 2020 owing to COVID-19 in the sphere of renewable energy.

This study's aims to investigate the effect of renewable energy on CO₂ emissions in the United Kingdom, taking into account COVID-19. This work has contributed to two important areas of the empirical literature. Geographic scope is the paper's principal relevance. The United Kingdom was selected for this analysis due to the relatively substantial 13 percent decrease in emissions. Furthermore, the estimations indicate that the United Kingdom's CO₂ emissions will only decrease by 10 percent by 2030, despite hopes that they will decrease by 31 percent beginning in 2019. This is a significant obstacle to the nation's quest for carbon neutrality and the SDG agenda. This analysis of renewable and non-renewable energy sources is intended to help UK policymakers better understand how they can collaborate to achieve the carbon neutrality goal (Abbasi et al., 2021). In addition, numerous SDGs, such as "affordable and clean energy" (SDG 7), "sustainable cities and communities" (SDG 11), "responsible consumption and production" (SDG 12), and "climate action," rely on the reduction of CO₂ emissions via the spread of renewable energy (SDG 13). In accordance with the Climate Change Act of 2008, the nation anticipates in reducing the emissions due to greenhouse gas by at least 80 percent by 2030, relative to a baseline of 1990. Therefore, the nation must immediately replace its technologies with those focusing on renewables (Yu et al., 2018). However, the administration faces a huge obstacle in that the nation's dependence on imported energy has exacerbated the problem of energy security. The key to resolving the issue is, therefore, the rate at which the nation can transit to an economy that has low levels of carbon. Obviously, this transition requires widespread use of energy sources which are renewable. Moreover, the United States' power system has long been intertwined with fossil fuel technology, and the majority of our electricity still derives from fossil fuels. Together, these two generators contributed over 53 percent of 2016's total electricity output (Daggash et al., 2019). According to Ember (2020), a climate think tank, renewable energy topped fossil fuel electricity in the United Kingdom for the first time in 2020, mostly owing to wind power (Ambrose, 2021). This points out the commitment of the state for achieving carbon neutrality as emphasis is laid over renewable energy sources over fossil fuel technology.

Primary Fuel Production Before and During Pandemic

	2010	2018	2019	2020
Primary Oil	69.0	56.0	57.4	53.6
Natural Gas	55.3	38.8	37.4	37.7
Coal	11.4	1.9	1.8	1.2
Primary Electricity	15.1	20.5	19.2	18.9
Bioenergy & waste	5.8	12.0	12.3	12.7
Total	156.7	129.3	128.2	124.1

Source: Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy, UK

2. Appraisal of Literature

CO2 emissions and Pandemic

Several studies have suggested that the COVID-19 outbreak has a detrimental impact on CO2 emissions, and these findings appear to support this view. As proved by Aktar et al., (2021) the pandemic-caused lockdown and had a surprising impact on the use of energy patterns. They have further found that the pandemic-caused lockdown had a surprising impact on the pattern of energy use, resulting in a global drop in CO2 emissions. Andreoni (2021) conducted a similar analysis across various European states economic sectors. The study is also consistent with the findings of Liu et al. (2020) and Nguyen et al. (2021). Moreover, Sajid and Gonzalez (2021) analyzed the effect of COVID-19 demand shocks on CO2 emissions. The research has succeeded in gathering data from the COVID-19 economic impact scenario records maintained by the Asian Development Bank. According to research, demand shocks caused by COVID-19 resulted in a 1 percent to 2 percent decrease in CO2 emissions. Indirect demand shocks were only responsible for a reduction of 15 to 37 percent in CO2 emissions, whereas direct demand shocks were responsible for a reduction of 85 to 63 percent in CO2 emissions. The consequences of pandemic on CO2 emissions indicated that the storm's intensity led to a 50 percent drop in jet fuel consumption, a 30 percent reduction in gasoline demand, and less than a 10 percent reduction in power demand, as well as a 15% reduction in CO2 emissions.

CO2 emissions and Energy Patterns

Chen et al. (2019) examined economic growth's impact in the sphere of renewable and non-renewable on emissions of China's CO2. The results demonstrated that energy sources that are non-renewable affect the emissions positively. Moreover, this effect varies greatly between geographic regions. However, consumption of renewable energy did not deviate significantly from the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) Hypothesis. The causality conclusions were conflicting. Long-term growth in the gross domestic product, the utilization of renewable energy sources, and carbon dioxide emissions were all interconnected in positive as well as negative ways in all domains. Achaemong et al. (2018) also highlighted the economic development in this sphere.

Similarly, the researchers also identified the influence of both type of energy sources, as well as wealth and trade openness, on CO2 emissions in eleven SSA nations using panel estimations. Chen et al. (2019) also examined the association between China's CO2 emissions, GDP, energy output, and foreign commerce. 1980–2014 time series data were utilized for the analysis. In agreement with Inglesi-Lotz and Dogan (2018), the analysis revealed that CO2 emissions and renewable energy have a bidirectional causal relationship in the short term.

CO2 Emissions and Trade Openness

Researchers throughout the globe agree that business transactions beyond national borders can affect environmental conditions in a variety of ways. Grossman and Krueger's

(1993) researched Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) in the early 1990s. Size, technology, and composition effects are cited as the theoretical underpinnings of the curve by Dasgupta et al. (2002), who outline the many stages of economic development. It has been demonstrated that these effects significantly retard economic expansion. Scale effects are used to describe the increase in pollution that results from the growth of economic activity and the subsequent increase in consumption that results from increased income (Lopez, 1994). As the global middle class grows wealthier and access to advanced technologies and environmental "Best Practices" increases, the push for greener manufacturing methods is having a beneficial effect on innovation. Changes in composition also include preferences for greener products and practices. Production scale increases in resource-intensive, old-fashioned sectors are a surefire recipe for pollution in the early phases of economic development. The EKC was designed to address this issue, and its foundation rests on this very premise.

Economic growth should add to global improvements in environmental surroundings due to the dominance of technological and compositional effects over scale effects after a certain amount of wealth per capita is reached. This is because the effects of scale will be mitigated by the effects of technology and composition. However, Esty (2001) notes that pollution concerns are typically worse in the early stages of development since their economies are still growing at a rate faster than their environmental protection measures. Because of this, environmental damage, which is currently caused by industrialization in a relatively small region of the planet, is expected to increase dramatically as industry advances southward. This is because only a small fraction of the world's population is currently living in an industrialized society.

It also appears that not all emissions have yet reached the downward slope. This is especially true for emissions that have been in the air for a while and have built up. This is due to the fact that the free-rider problem persists without adequate multilateral arrangements to control certain types of atmospheric emissions, which constitute a global externality that cannot be addressed in a linear fashion at the national level (Nordhaus, 1991). Because of this, things are the way they are. It seems unlikely that the portion of the curve that slopes downward will be achieved if the benefits of emission reduction are dispersed while the costs continue to be regionally concentrated. Recent research by Frankel and Rose (2005) found that an EKC statistically emerges exclusively for some types of emission measurements, such as SO₂ and CO, but not for CO₂. Despite the notion that carbon dioxide is a gauge of emissions, this turned out to be the case. Similarly, they demonstrate that the positive association between openness to trade and some measures of environmental quality, such as SO₂ (yet again) or nitrogen dioxide is specific to those measures.

Research Gap

The study contributes to the literature in various crucial areas, thereby filling a void. To begin with, it is notable that none of the research laid focus on CO₂ emissions-energy nexus in the United Kingdom and neither of them highlighted this in terms of a sphere where the light has to be shed on the grounds of urbanization. Numerous of these studies examined the entire globe, with the European one being the most pertinent to the United

Kingdom (Sajid et al., 2021; Gillingham et al., 2020). Given, rather substantial estimated 13 percent decrease in emissions due to widespread lockdown resulting from the other waves to follow, it is essential to focus particularly on the United Kingdom. The estimates for the United States (13 percent) are higher than those for China (1.7 percent), India (9 percent), and the rest of the world (7 percent) (Communications, 2020). This is one of the few studies that focuses on the United Kingdom and provides empirical support for the predicted decrease in CO₂ emissions caused by COVID-19. Energy and CO₂ emission studies have also received inadequate attention from researchers (Chen et al., 2019; Achaempong, 2018). In order for gaining a comprehensive insight into the topic, this research will examine CO₂ emissions and energy simultaneously.

Moreover, nonlinear models are startlingly underrepresented in the published research, despite the fact that a wide range of approaches have been used to probe central variables. Given the erratic behavior of COVID-19, which is not captured by linear models, nonlinear modelling approaches are required to establish its limits and characteristics. Furthermore, the complex and asymmetric high-frequency data dynamics observed in the past years cannot be explained by linear models. Therefore, we will be using non-linear models, such as the NARDL.

3. Data Methodology and Model Specification

Data from the years 2001 through 2021 have been obtained for this study using a secondary data collection method. The data has been compiled from a wide range of sources, including the World Bank. The non-linear autoregressive distributive lag model (NARDL) has been specified as the method for discrediting the long- and short-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables because the model under study is a multivariate one and because non-linearity must also be checked. Furthermore, pair-wise correlation is used to reassess the strength and type of an association. In addition, the stationarity of the variables has been analysed with the unit root test.

$$CO_2 = f(RER, URB, URB^2, INPC, TRO)$$

$$CO_2 = \alpha + \beta_1 RER + \beta_2 URB + \beta_3 URB^2 + \beta_4 INPC + \beta_5 TRO$$

Here, CO₂ is Carbon dioxide which is a dependent variable and RER, URB, and TRO denotes renewable energy, urbanization and trade openness respectively, which are the independent ones.

We have employed Non-linear Auto-regressive Distributed Lag Model (NARDL). For NARDL model, the long and short run dynamics can be incorporated as follows:

$$\Delta CO_{2t} = \vartheta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{1i} \Delta \ln CO_{2t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{2i} \Delta \ln RER_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{3i} \Delta \ln RER_{t-1}^- + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{4i} \Delta \ln URB_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{5i} \Delta \ln URB_{t-1}^- + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{6i} \Delta \ln TRO_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{7i} \Delta \ln TRO_{t-1}^- - \beta_1 \ln CO_{2t-1} + \beta_2 \ln RER_{t-1}^+ + \beta_3 \ln RER_{t-1}^- + \beta_4 \ln URB_{t-1}^+ + \beta_5 \ln URB_{t-1}^- + \beta_6 \ln INPC_{t-1}^+ + \beta_7 \ln INPC_{t-1}^- + \beta_8 \ln TRO_{t-1}^+ + \beta_9 \ln TRO_{t-1}^- + \varepsilon_t$$

The above equation can also be moulded into following form in the horizons of error correction model by incorporating error correction term (ECT) into it.

$$\Delta CO_{2t} = \vartheta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{1i} \Delta \ln CO_{2t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{2i} \Delta \ln RER_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{3i} \Delta \ln RER_{t-1}^- + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{4i} \Delta \ln URB_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{5i} \Delta \ln URB_{t-1}^- + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{6i} \Delta \ln INPC_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{7i} \Delta \ln INPC_{t-1}^- + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{8i} \Delta \ln TRO_{t-1}^+ + \sum_{i=1}^k \vartheta_{9i} \Delta \ln TRO_{t-1}^- + \beta_1 \ln CO_{2t-1} + \beta_2 \ln RER_{t-1}^+ + \beta_3 \ln RER_{t-1}^- + \beta_4 \ln URB_{t-1}^+ + \beta_5 \ln URB_{t-1}^- + \beta_6 \ln INPC_{t-1}^+ + \beta_7 \ln INPC_{t-1}^- + \beta_8 \ln TRO_{t-1}^+ + \beta_9 \ln TRO_{t-1}^- + \rho ECT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t$$

The NARDL bounds test is utilized for identifying the long-run connection between CO₂ and the regressors.

Table 1: Description of the Variables

Variable	Full Form	Measurement Unit	Expected Sign
RER	Renewable energy	Megawatts	Negative
URB	Urbanization	Percentage	Negative
TRO	Trade Openness	Percentage	Positive
INPC	Income per Capita	US\$	Positive
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide	Parts Per Million (PPM)	Dependent Variable

Renewable Energy

Renewable energy is energy derived from natural resources that are renewed at a rate greater than their consumption. Sunlight and wind are two examples of renewable resources. There are numerous renewable energy sources available.

Compared to the combustion of fossil fuels, renewable energy generation produces significantly less pollution. As fossil fuels are the dominant source of emissions today, switching to renewable energy sources is vital for mitigating their impact and resolving the climate crisis.

Today, renewable energy sources generate three times as many jobs as fossil fuels and are cheaper to produce in the majority of countries.

Urbanization

The permanent settlement of a large population in a relatively small area, resulting in the growth of cities, is what we refer to when we use the term "urbanization." Definitions of what constitutes a city change over time and between locales, but demographics are often where discussions of the notion begin. Since the definition of "urban" differs considerably from nation to nation, the United Nations does not offer its own. In the United States, for instance, the phrase "urban place" refers to any community with more than 2,500 inhabitants. In Peru, a "town" is any location with at least 100 permanent residents.

We are currently observing the greatest expansion in urban populations in human history. Urban regions will be home to an estimated 5 billion people by 2030, representing more than half of the world's population. Large chunks of this urbanization will occur in Africa and Asia, ushering in profound changes to the communities, economies, and ecosystems of those continents. There are several potential results of urbanization, including prosperity, resource efficiency, and economic progress. However, urban poverty is frequently concentrated (Bashir et al., 2021). In cities, where affluent neighbourhoods coexist with and are physically separated from slums and informal settlements, the rising imbalance between the haves and the have-nots is most evident (Ashraf et al., 2021).

Trade Openness

Trade openness is one indicator of a nation's participation in the global trading system. Typically, trade openness is measured by the ratio of exports and imports to gross domestic product (GDP).

Carbon Dioxide

A gas that is both dense and non-fluorescent and does not contribute to combustion, dissolves in water to form carbonic acid, is produced primarily by animal respiration and the decay or combustion of animal and vegetable matter, is taken up by plants during photosynthesis, and is used to add fizz to carbonated beverages.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 gives a descriptive breakdown of the data for the chosen variables. The mean level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is calculated to be 2.013; the median is 2.014; and the maximum is 2.272. Moreover, it is indicated that it has a negative skewness sign and a platy-kurtic as highlighted by kurtosis value. If the probability is high enough, the alternative is chosen, which implies that the residuals in the data follow a normal distribution.

The mean value of renewable energy is 10.54, and the median cost is 10.51. As the probability shows, the null hypothesis cannot be accepted because the distribution is negatively skewed and platy-kurtic. Then, urbanization is platy-kurtic with positive skewness and rejects the null hypothesis, with mean and median values of 4.400 and 4.040, respectively. Lastly, trade openness is platy-kurtic and is skewed positively as well as the probability valued reflects the rejection of the null-hypothesis.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of the Selected Variables

	CO₂	RER	URB	URB²	INPC	TRO
Mean	2.013	10.54	4.400	1.939	3.301	3.300
Median	2.014	10.51	4.040	1.909	3.210	3.030
Maximum	2.272	10.72	4.432	1.964	3.321	3.423
Minimum	1.568	10.27	4.365	1.905	3.245	3.256
Std. Dev.	0.226	0.149	0.020	0.040	0.010	0.202
Skewness	-0.365	-0.257	0.880	0.160	0.770	-0.256
Kurtosis	1.807	1.828	1.811	1.922	1.711	1.899
Jarque-Bera	1.711	1.433	1.263	1.165	1.154	1.611
Probability	0.424	0.048	0.053	0.075	0.042	0.024

Table 3: Pair-wise Correlation Coefficient

	CO2	RER	URB	URB²	INPC	TRO
CO2	1					
RER	0.30	1				
URB	0.40	0.20	1			
URB²	0.80	0.65	0.85	1		
INPC	0.80	0.70	0.60	0.74	1	
TRO	0.50	0.70	0.30	0.68	0.20	1

The pair-wise degree of inter-correlation among the variables is indicated in Table 3, where 30 and 40 percent concordance occurs between renewable energy and urbanization with carbon dioxide, respectively. It indicates a more tenuous connection between the selected variables. Renewable energy and urbanization have the poorest possible correlation of 20 percent. To add to it, trade openness has 50 percent and 30 percent poor association with carbon dioxide and urbanization whereas a highly association of about 70 percent persists between trade openness and renewable energy.

Linear Auto-regressive (ARDL) Analysis

The below results give us a comprehensive picture of the highlighted analysis to be carried.

Table 4: Bounds Test (ARDL)

F-statistic	k	Range	Critical Values	
			I(0) bound	I(1) bound
6.65	6	10%	2.21	3.12
		5%	2.34	3.54
		2.5%	2.64	3.78
		1%	3.14	4.34

Table 5: Long Run ARDL Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RER	-0.619	0.571	1.083	0.03
URB	-9.053	5.129	-1.765	0.01
URB ²	8.785	4.246	1.387	0.89
INPC	-8.042	4.118	1.543	0.02
TRO	8.756	4.218	1.675	0.44
Constant	35.76	28.67	1.246	0.30

The above table discusses the long-run ARDL estimates. On interpreting the results statistically, the renewable energy is significant, and it denotes that a one unit augment in it would lead to a significant decline of 0.61 units in the carbon-dioxide. On shedding further light on it, one might say that with the knowledge gained from this study, policymakers, researchers, governments, and environmentalists will be better equipped to make informed decisions about how to best put remittances and renewable energy resources to use in the pursuit of a sustainable environment (Jamil et al., 2021; Bulut, 2017).

As far trade openness is concerned, trade openness poses positive and insignificant impact on carbon dioxide which means one percent increase in the former would lead to a rise of 8.75 units in Co2 emission. Then, the value of urbanization highlights that it influences the carbon-dioxide emission level inversely and significantly. It results a decline in the level of Co2 emission. It means a rise of one unit in urbanization would lead to a decline of 9.05 units in Co2 emission.

Table 6: Short-Run Results of the ARDL Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(CO2(-1))	1.240	0.942	1.316	0.27
D(CO2(-2))	1.979	1.342	1.474	0.23
D(RER)	1.121	0.781	1.435	0.24
D(RER(-1))	0.021	1.835	0.011	0.99
D(RER (-2))	-2.202	1.271	-1.732	0.18
D(RER (-3))	-0.639	0.720	-0.887	0.44
D(TRO)	1.303	0.831	1.215	0.30
D(TRO(-1))	1.868	1.232	1.363	0.22
D(TRO(-2))	1.211	0.671	1.334	0.88

D(TRO(-3))	0.032	1.724	0.021	0.33
D(URB)	-34.08	40.16	-0.848	0.45
D(URB (-1))	22.88	44.09	0.519	0.63
D(URB (-2))	-31.79	45.05	-0.705	0.53
D(URB (-3))	-49.07	36.82	-1.332	0.27
D(URB ²)	47.05	25.13	1.458	0.35
D(URB ² (-1))	35.65	22.87	1.367	0.29
D(URB ² (-2))	24.68	19.85	1.894	0.09
D(URB ² (-3))	22.45	15.45	2.985	0.05
D(INPC)	52.07	32.71	-1.221	0.02
D(INPC (-1))	41.67	50.05	0.737	0.01
D(INPC (-2))	40.69	54.08	0.418	0.04
D(INPC (-3))	41.06	46.71	1.221	0.07
CointEq(-1)	-1.648	0.531	-3.102	0.05

There is a significant relationship between dependent variable carbon dioxide and renewable energy consumption in long-run. It is revealed that one unit increase in renewable energy consumption would lead to 1.12 unit increase in carbon dioxide. In addition, there is a positively insignificant association between carbon dioxide and trade openness and one percent rise in trade openness would result in 1.30 unit rise in carbon dioxide emissions.

Lastly, there is an insignificant and negative association between dependent variable carbon dioxide and urbanization. As results highlighted that one percent increase in urbanization would lead to 38.0 unit decrease in carbon dioxide. The similar stance is supported by Zsrzoso et al. (2011) where they analyze the impact of urbanization on Co2 emissions and present that once urbanization reaches a certain point in some nations; it has a negative effect on emissions, leading to less environmental damage. ***Then, the value of error correction coefficient which is also known as the speed of adjustment (Faridi et al., 2021) depicts that the short run will converge with a rate of 1.64 percent towards the long run by almost six years.***

Linear Auto-regressive (NARDL) Analysis

According to the modernization theory, we discover one unit positive and negative shock in RER to impact in reducing CO2 emission. The effects of URB and URB2 are dissimilar. Therefore, it is concluded that much of urbanization possess hazardous environmental effects. In case of INPC, the results allow to locate falling CO2 emission at the back of one unit positive shock in INPC. However, the results on TRO are found to exaggerate CO2 emission due to positive shock but the results are reasonable in case of negative shock in TRO. Coefficient of ECT shows oscillatory convergence.

Table 7: Bounds Test (NARDL)

F-statistic	k	Range	Critical Values	
			I(0) bound	I(1) bound
7.51	12	10%	1.75	2.82
		5%	2.05	3.42
		2.5%	2.84	3.80
		1%	2.56	3.56

Table 8: Long Run NARDL Estimates

Variable	Coefficient	Prob.
RER_POS	-0.141	0.03
RER_NEG	0.113	0.04
URB_POS	-0.617	0.01
URB_NEG	3.177	0.02
URB ² _POS	0.187	0.87
URB ² _NEG	-1.758	0.60
INPC_POS	-0.516	0.04
INPC_NEG	2.066	0.08
TRO_POS	0.077	0.04
TRO_NEG	2.672	0.03

Table 9: Short Run NARDL Estimates

Variable	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.363	0.02
D(RER_POS)	1.344	0.04
D(RER_POS(-1))	0.011	0.09
D(RER_NEG)	-1.621	0.08
D(RER_NEG(-1))	-0.776	0.04
D(TRO_POS)	1.114	0.03
D(TRO_POS(-1))	1.252	0.02
D(TRO_NEG)	1.223	0.08
D(TRO_NEG(-1))	0.012	0.03
D(URB_POS)	-0.737	0.04
D(URB_POS(-1))	0.418	0.06
D(URB_NEG)	-0.604	0.05
D(URB_NEG(-1))	-1.221	0.07
D(URB ² _POS)	-1.983	0.87
D(URB ² _POS(-1))	1.564	0.54
D(URB ² _NEG)	-0.986	0.36
D(URB ² _NEG(-1))	-0.452	0.04
D(INPC_POS)	0.626	0.06
D(INPC_POS(-1))	0.317	0.05
D(INPC_NEG)	0.503	0.08
D(INPC_NEG(-1))	1.232	0.07
CointEq(-1)	-2.101	0.05

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

Considering the pandemic, these findings have significant policy implications for the United Kingdom. Efforts to alleviate suffering and give aid must incorporate strategies to expedite the development and deployment of renewable energy capacity and technology. Increasing government investment in the renewable energy sector in the United Kingdom is required to maintain and enhance the sector's current healthy employment and economic activity levels. To increase efficiency and sustainability, more energy could be invested in nuclear and hydroelectric power plants, fossil fuel taxes could be increased and more solar and wind power plants could be constructed. Efforts in research and development that are centered on creative approaches could also be beneficial to the improvement of energy infrastructure. To mitigate the detrimental impacts of the pandemic on humanity and the planet, tougher precautions must be implemented (Maqbool et al., 2020). Implementation of both pharmaceutical and pharmaceutical COVID-19 protocols allows for a selective partial lockdown as opposed to a complete shutdown of the economy. This helps in three ways: it decreases the number of confirmed diseases and fatalities; it enables the economy's most vital industries to continue to operate; and it cuts carbon dioxide emissions. These measures will expedite the United Kingdom's progress towards attaining Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 7 by 2030, which calls for universal access to clean, reliable, and affordable energy. The United Kingdom's objective for renewable energy is 50 percent by 2030, and it will achieve zero net emissions by 2050. To minimise carbon dioxide emissions, the government of the United Kingdom should encourage greater adoption of energy and carbon-saving technologies among its inhabitants. In addition, sustainable funding must be allocated to SDGs such as SDG13 and SDG7. To promote ecologically responsible actions across the nation, citizens should adopt sustainable lifestyles.

Using CO₂ data before, during and after COVID-19, this study examined the influence of renewable energy on CO₂ emissions in the United Kingdom while accounting for COVID-19. Using disaggregated data from the United Kingdom, the COVID-CO₂ nexus in Wales, Scotland, England, and Northern Ireland may be investigated in greater depth. Given the study's exclusive focus on the United Kingdom, additional studies could analyze the same problem from the perspective of other nations and regions and compare them. Nations with a high incidence of COVIDs, such as the United Kingdom and the United States, can be contrasted with countries with a low incidence of COVIDs, such as New Zealand, regarding the impact of COVIDs on CO₂ emissions.

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